

PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE FOOD INDUSTRY OF OUR COUNTRY

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Abstract: The article focuses on providing the population with food industry products and directions of development of this industry. From the first days of the independence of our republic, the main attention was paid to increasing the production of food products, that is, ensuring food safety, continuous and sufficient supply of food products to the population was defined as one of the important tasks. In particular, the volume of production of agricultural products has more than doubled.

Key words: Food, humanity, fruits and vegetables, safe, industry, export, climate, meat-milk, milk-fat, oil-oil, fish products, flour-groats, pasta, fruit- canned vegetables, juices, various drinks, sugar, confectionery, bread.

Enter It is known that the food industry is a wide branch of the national economy that produces food products, which includes meat and milk, milk and butter, oil and fish products, flour and cereals, pasta, fruit enterprises that produce canned vegetables, juices, various drinks, sugar, confectionery, bread and other delicacies are incorporated. It's no secret that today the issue of food production and its supply is one of the global problems. This problem is equally important for developed and developing countries. In this sense, meeting the demand for food products of the population of our republic with quality products is an urgent issue.

As the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, noted, the difference between the rapid increase in the population of the Earth and the limited opportunities for growth in the production of food products is the main reason why the issue of solving the food program is becoming increasingly acute year by year. I think there is no need to talk about the reason today. Simply put, the growth of food production is lagging behind the growth of population and needs. This gap is deepening, first of all, in countries and regions where there are no suitable conditions for the rapid production of food products. First of all, environmental degradation continues, unpredictable effects of climate change, frequent droughts and shortage of water resources, including groundwater for irrigation. is running out, insufficient investments in irrigation, land reclamation, and restoration of land fertility. Ecological degradation of the land is increasing due to the constant use of chemicals, mineral fertilizers and pesticides. Urbanization, i.e. urbanization processes, problems related to population migration from villages to cities are also added to these.

As a result, the arable land for growing food products is shrinking significantly, and the needs of the population are not being fully met. Also, it cannot be ignored that in a number of Asian countries, such as China and India, the income of the population is growing at a rapid pace,

and the consumption of food products is increasing accordingly. One of the negative factors is the huge losses in the delivery of food products to the consumer under the "field to table" scheme. From the first days of the independence of our republic, the main attention was paid to increasing the production of food products, that is, ensuring food safety, continuous and sufficient supply of food products to the population was defined as one of the important tasks. In particular, the volume of production of agricultural products has more than doubled. Despite the fact that the population of our country has increased by almost 10 million people or more than 30 percent, the per capita consumption of meat has increased by 1.3 times, milk and dairy products by 1.6 times, potatoes by 1.7 times, made it possible to increase vegetables more than 2 times and fruits almost 4 times, about 16 million tons of fruits and vegetables are grown in our country every year. About 300 kilograms of vegetables, 75 kilograms of potatoes and 44 kilograms of grapes are available per capita. This is three times more than the optimal consumption rate, which is considered acceptable.

3.3 of the five priorities for the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev No. PF-4947 dated February 7, 2017. In paragraph "Modernization and rapid development of agriculture", a decision was made to further strengthen the country's food security, expand the production of environmentally friendly products, and significantly increase the export potential of the agricultural sector. At the moment, the food association unites about 200 enterprises belonging to fruit and vegetable processing, meat-milk, fat-oil and other sectors of the food industry, and has a system of mutual relations with them both horizontally and vertically. is set to . If three years ago the oil and tobacco industries accounted for a significant share in the food industry, now, due to structural changes, more than 60 percent of products are processed in fruit and vegetable processing, meat and dairy, and confectionery. and other food products.

The doubling of the average annual number of employees in small business enterprises also made it possible to further develop the activities of enterprises. During the past 3 years since the establishment of the food association, 121 projects have been implemented by the association enterprises, and 198.4 mln. dollar investment was absorbed.

Based on this, if we analyze the level of food supply of the population by local producers in 2014, meat and meat products are 98.6 percent, milk and dairy products are 99.8 percent, percent, pasta products made up 95.4 percent, margarine 77.7 percent, sugar 92.9 percent, confectionery 68.5 percent. Today, food security is fully ensured in the republic, and more than 90 percent of the population's need for food products is provided at the expense of local production enterprises.

It is required to reduce the share of imports in providing the population with food products, or to increase the number of enterprises that produce high-quality and world-class food products in the country without imports, or to implement innovation projects in existing enterprises. In this regard, in our opinion, it is necessary to improve cooperation with the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan and research institutions..

As a result of the implementation of innovation projects, tax incentives are applied to enterprises that have organized the production of quality products, and it is also beneficial to direct the saved funds to the development of the enterprise.

In addition, it is necessary to further increase the level of full use of the capacities of enterprises processing agricultural products. For this, it will be necessary to form a raw material base, that is, to supply enterprises with raw materials.

Since ancient times, the food industry has been a sector that satisfies the basic needs of the population. Today, it is an urgent issue to ensure the stable economic growth of the country, the well-being of the population, social protection of the population, and the provision of necessary primary products. In order to solve this problem, it is necessary to increase the attraction of foreign investments for the purpose of effective use of available resources, improvement, modernization and diversification of food industry enterprises. As a result, it becomes possible to improve food production technologies and speed up the production process, introduce new production lines, increase the type and quality of products, and fully satisfy the needs of the population for consumer goods.

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